

**THE TORSIONAL FATIGUE CHARACTERISTICS OF
UNIDIRECTIONAL GLASS REINFORCED MATERIALS**

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes work in support of the development of a composite material system for the construction of a bearingless rotor linkage for a helicopter. Rigid matrix composites with a complex H cross-section can be designed to have the required flexural rigidities coupled with a low torsional rigidity. However, the torsional characteristics in fatigue of these components are relatively unknown.

The work is concerned with the torsional characteristics of simple circular section unidirectional glass composites with Ciba Geigy 913 epoxide resin, tested both statically and in fatigue, and with similar measurements on components made from this composite material but with a Complex H section.

INTRODUCTION

Present day helicopter main rotor hubs are either semi-rigid or articulated relying on one or more bearings to allow the necessary blade motions. To simplify construction and cost and to reduce maintenance, weight and aerodynamic drag, attempts are being made to develop bearingless main rotor systems. These have no mechanical hinges and instead blade lag, flap and pitch are accommodated by flexing and twisting of the rotor head material. The structural connection between the rotor hub and the blade is required to have high flexural rigidity, tailorable in two orthogonal directions, coupled with low torsional rigidity and adequate fatigue strength and strain characteristics. Semi-rigid systems have been successfully developed to accommodate blade lag and flap deflections within the construction material. However, it is more difficult to

accommodate the torsional feathering without the use of a bearing. A low torsional rigidity is necessary to minimise control system weight and power. This can be achieved by two main approaches. These are:

- (i) to use composite materials fabricated using compliant matrices with relatively simple cross sections,
- (ii) to use traditional rigid matrix composites but with complex thin walled open sections of low moment of inertia. These sections can be designed to give the required rigidities in flexure and torsion. Structural coupling effects are minimised by employing a cross section with two axes of symmetry. The design of the section to evolve from studies at Westlands is known as a double H section.

It is the second approach which is considered in this paper.

Though data exist on the tension/compression and short beam shear fatigue of unidirectional glass composites, little information relating to the torsional fatigue behaviour of composites is available in the literature, and the torsional characteristics in fatigue of complex section components is even less well researched. This paper will describe some static and fatigue results obtained from unidirectional glass reinforced epoxide samples with simple circular section and components of a complex section.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A Schenck torsional fatigue machine of maximum capacity ± 4 kNm was used in both static and fatigue experiments. Data relating to torques, maximum and minimum torques, shear strains, surface temperatures and number of fatigue cycles were monitored as appropriate by a PET computer linked through an IEEE interface to a CIL-conditioning system. Specially written data collection and analysis programs were used to give semi-continuous monitoring to detect failure and present the appropriate results in graphical form. For the low frequencies, < 0.5 Hz, used in the static tests an x-y chart recorder was also used to record the torque-twist curves.

Static Measurements on Circular Section Samples

The samples used were machined to 25 mm diameter from 25 mm square section unidirectional glass reinforced epoxide (913 resin) moulded bars. The central gauge length was 125 mm with an overall sample length of 225 mm. Strain gauge rosettes, bonded at the centre of the specimen, were used to monitor the strains at $+ 45^\circ$ to the specimen axis and hence the shear strain on the component. An acoustic emission transducer, coupled through silicone grease, was also placed on the sample in order to monitor the acoustic signals emitted from the sample as the torsional load was applied. A 35 kHz high pass filter and 0.1 to 1 MHz Bandpass filter allowed the background noise to be filtered such that only signals originating from the specimen were monitored. The torque on the sample was measured using a precalibrated torsional load cell on the static head of the Schenck torsion machine.

Two samples were stressed incrementally and hysteresis loops were measured as a function of the peak torque levels. The stiffnesses of the samples were calculated using shear strain measurements obtained from both

strain gauges and from angular rotations of the torsion machine. The tests were stopped after specimen failure had occurred.

Fatigue Measurements on Circular Section Samples

Constant strain amplitude fatigue tests were performed mostly at 5 Hz, close to the expected rotor frequency, with sinusoidally varying torsional amplitude of $\pm 0^\circ$. The angular rotations were adjusted using the Schenck controls to give the required values for the initial fatigue torques. The minimum and maximum fatigue torques were monitored as a function of the number of cycles. Surface temperatures were also recorded and in some cases the acoustic emission signals and the maximum torques were recorded on an x-t recorder. The samples were fatigued until either a step decrease in the peak torques supported was obtained, indicative of a fatigue failure, or until 5×10^6 cycles were reached.

Static Measurements on Complex H Samples

Two complex H section glass reinforced composite beams were tested in torsion. The cross-sectional shape is indicated in Fig. 1 and dimensions were 71 x 98 mm. The test samples were ~ 700 mm long bonded for 30 mm at each end of the specimen by a cold setting polyurethane rubber into aluminium end fittings which could be bolted to the torsion machine. The (cross-section) geometry of the end pieces is shown in Fig. 1. Four 2 mm stacked strain gauge rosettes were bonded at a central position along the length of the specimen at accurately set positions. The gauges were aligned at $+45^\circ$ to the specimen axis such that the shear strains could be measured at the surface of the specimen. Specimens were tested up to torques of ~ 125 Nm and the measured elastic strains were compared to the calculated finite element strains. The overall torsional rigidity was measured using deflections obtained from a split laser beam projected onto small mirrors bonded onto the sample. By monitoring the positions of the reflected beams on a graduated scale, as a function of the applied torque, accurate values for the torsional rigidity of the specimen were obtained.

Fatigue Measurements on Complex H Samples

Fatigue tests between predetermined angles were carried out on the two complex H samples immediately after the static stiffness tests. The torque levels were chosen such that peak surface shear stresses on the sample were ~ 22 MPa. The appropriate torque levels were determined from the static strain measurements and the computed stress distribution using the finite element analysis. The shear modulus of the composite was assumed to be 4.2 GPa. The peak torques and specimen surface temperatures were monitored as a function of the number of fatigue cycles applied to the specimen. The angular rotations were also followed during the fatigue tests at 5.4 Hz using the laser optical lever arrangement.

The specimens were examined at intervals to see if any cracking could be observed. However, it was not possible to observe the first 30 mm from each end of the specimens which were masked by the grips. Careful static tests at the end of the fatigue tests were carried out to remeasure the torsional rigidity of the samples.

In sample CH1 the cracked regions at the specimen ends were cut off, the torsional gauge length reduced, and the sample was stressed to give hysteresis loops. The magnitudes of the stresses were increased until cracking of the specimen was observed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Static Measurements on Circular Section Samples

A typical torque/strain curve to failure is given in Fig. 2. The specimen has an initial modulus of 4.5 GPa, departs from linearity at 23 MPa and fails at 264 Nm equivalent to an apparent shear stress, τ_o , of 90 MPa. However, for non-linear systems it is necessary to apply a Nadai [1] correction factor to calculate the corrected stress τ_a . This is achieved from the τ_o/γ curve such that

$$\tau_o = 2Q/\pi a^3$$

and

$$\tau_a = \frac{3}{4}\tau_o + \frac{\gamma d\tau_o}{4d\gamma}$$

where Q is the applied torque
 a is the specimen radius
 γ is the shear strain

A master curve of the Nadai corrected stress against uncorrected stress was constructed. The torsional moduli, calculated from the slopes of the hysteresis loops, against τ_a are given in Fig. 3 which shows the results for two samples. Very little acoustic emission was observed up to $\tau_a \sim 49$ MPa after which the emission increased until failure at $\tau_a = 80.7$ MPa when a longitudinal crack was observed running along the whole specimen length.

Results of Fatigue Measurements on Circular Section Samples

The cyclic stress level had a marked effect on the specimen's response to fatigue. In all specimens the surface temperatures increased above ambient as a result of hysteresis of the composite materials when subjected to torsion. The increase in temperature was associated with a corresponding reduction in the peak torques measured as the sample was fatigued over a constant shear strain. At 5 Hz, for equilibrium stresses < 29 MPa the surface temperature reached equilibrium after which there was little reduction in peak torque until ultimate failure occurred. Fig. 4 shows the \pm peak stress and the measured specimen surface temperature against number of fatigue cycles. An indication of the magnitude of the acoustic emission signals is also shown schematically. There was a step increase in acoustic emission at 32.2 K cycles but no corresponding change in stress amplitude or equilibrium surface temperature. The large reduction in peak shear stress at 51 K cycles is associated with specimen failure by a longitudinal crack running across the whole length of the specimen. This failure is associated with a slight increase in the equilibrium temperature and a step increase in the acoustic emission signal. The equilibrium

temperature stabilised at 56°C after ~ 22 K cycles and it is clear that the initial fall in peak stress is a direct consequence of the hysteretic heating. As the specimen failed at 51 K cycles the temperature rose strongly and then began to fall. A linear reduction of the peak stress amplitude and specimen temperature was observed during fatigue up to failure.

For higher stress levels > 30 MPa the surface temperature increased rapidly, and failure occurred before the equilibrium temperature could be reached. In these cases the peak torque amplitude decreased progressively until failure occurred. Fig. 5 illustrates this effect. The peak torque fell approximately linearly with the number of fatigue cycles up to ~ 1500 cycles. This corresponds to a linear increase in surface temperature. Specimen failure occurred at 1600 cycles after which the equilibrium temperature decreased. This effect is purely a consequence of the thermocouple position. At this stress level the failure was associated with the thermal runaway. Damage occurred locally and caused a local increase in temperature, producing a radial damage zone. This was restrained by the low thermal conductivity of the glass composite causing the heat flow to be low along the specimen length. In this experiment the thermocouple was several centimetres away from the hot zone which developed a temperature of $\sim 170^\circ\text{C}$ during the fatigue test. The shear along the specimen length became non-linear with the majority of the twist occurring in the damaged 'hot' portion of the gauge length.

Some comparative fatigue tests were carried out at 2.5 and 1 Hz at stress levels between 32 and 27 MPa. At the lower frequencies considerably reduced equilibrium temperatures were monitored and higher fatigue lives by a factor of > 2 were obtained over those predicted from the 5 Hz fatigue data.

The effect of equilibrium fatigue stress on the equilibrium specimen temperature is shown in Fig. 6. The temperature increases linearly with stress at both 5 Hz and 1 Hz test frequency. Reducing the frequency of the test has the effect of reducing the equilibrium temperature reached, which causes an increase in the number of fatigue cycles to failure.

The results obtained from the torsional fatigue of the circular section unidirectional glass composite samples are summarised in Fig. 7. This shows the peak cyclic stress and equilibrium specimen temperature as a function of the number of fatigue cycles to failure. There is remarkably little scatter in these fatigue results, and where there is, fibre misalignment in the specimen was observed, which was responsible for the premature failure of the specimen. The fatigue curve is quite flat at the high cycle end. Run out at 5×10^6 cycles would be expected at initial stress levels of 22 MPa and little hysteretic heating would be expected. This value corresponds quite closely to 23 MPa determined as the stress at which non-linear effects are first observed in the torque/twist curves.

Results of Static Testing of Complex H Samples

Table 1 gives the results obtained for the torsional rigidity of the two complex H samples tested. The initial rigidities measured using the laser optics agreed closely with the results obtained from angular rotations of the Schenck torsion head, provided the total specimen length was used in the calculation. The rigidity after fatigue was very similar to the

rigidities measured before fatigue even though cracking during fatigue had occurred in both samples. The rigidities of the complex H samples were $\approx 25.7 \text{ Nm/deg.m}^{-1}$.

TABLE 1
Torsional rigidities measured in complex H samples
before and after fatigue testing

Sample	Laser Torsional Stiffness	Schenck Stiffness	Cycle
	Nm/deg.m^{-1}		
CH1	25.89	25.68	1
CH1	25.71	25.65	5×10^6
CH2	25.61	25.34	1
CH2	25.70	25.2	1×10^6

The strain gauge results of the static testing of the complex H samples are summarised for both specimens in Table 2. The gauge positions correspond to the positions marked in Fig. 8, which also shows the predicted stress contours using finite element techniques on two sections subjected to torsion. The stresses indicated on Fig. 8 are for a twist per unit length equivalent to 5 radians mm^{-1} and assume a shear modulus for the glass composite of 4.2 GPa. The value of k is the stress concentration factor relating the predicted maximum stress (which occurs at the central fillets) to the stress at the gauge position. The slopes (s) are obtained during the elastic torsion test between $\pm \sim 125 \text{ Nm}$. The maximum torque (Q) is that torque predicted to give a maximum shear stress (τ) on the specimen of 22 MPa. This is calculated from:

$$Q = \tau s / kG$$

where G is the shear modulus of the unidirectional glass composite. The average torque values required to give a shear stress of 22 MPa for samples CH1 and CH2 were $251 \pm 20 \text{ Nm}$ and $233 \pm 12 \text{ Nm}$ respectively.

Also included in the table are the predicted slopes for each gauge position as estimated from the finite element predictions and the measured initial torsional rigidities of the samples. The errors between the predicted slopes and the measured slopes are within $\pm 8\%$.

The central uncracked portion of this sample was tested statically until crack initiation was observed. The apparent rigidity decreases with increasing torque falling from an initial value of 25.7 to $20.8 \text{ Nm/deg.m}^{-1}$ just before crack initiation. The first audible crack was heard at a torque of 1068 Nm but no obvious change in the slope of the torque/twist curve was observed. The crack, which occurred at the right-hand side of the

specimen close to the grips was observed to grow at torques of ≥ 1000 Nm. A torque of 1068 Nm is equivalent to a uncorrected stress of 96 MPa. Assuming a Nadai correction similar to the circular section specimens, this is equivalent to a corrected shear stress for failure of 82.5 MPa which is in good agreement with the failure stresses measured in the simple circular section samples.

TABLE 2
Static torsional results in complex H samples

(a) Complex H - Sample 1 (CH1)

Gauge Position	k	Measured Slope Nm/ ϵ	Estimated Torque for a 22 MPa Maximum Shear Stress, Nm	Predicted Slope Nm/ ϵ	% Error
1	1.7516	Gauge failure	-	86078	-
2	2.2305	117200	275.2	110427	5.9
3	3.0697	140692	240.1	150849	-6.9
4	1.9870	90674	239.0	97659	-7.4
Average			<u>251</u> \pm 20		

(b) Complex H - Sample 2 (CH2)

Gauge Position	k	Measured Slope Nm/ ϵ	Predicted Torque for 22 MPa Nm	Predicted Slope Nm/ ϵ	% Error
1	1.7516	83687	250.3	85150	-1.7
2	2.2305	97044	227.9	109230	-11.8
3	3.0697	128228	218.8	149200	-15.0
4	1.9870	89928	237.1	96600	-7.1
Average			<u>233</u> \pm 12		

Results of Fatigue Testing of Complex H Samples

Two complex H samples were fatigue tested at 5.4 Hz.

Results for sample 1 (CH1)

Initial torques of + 276 Nm were used in this fatigue test equivalent to a peak stress of 24.2 MPa. The equilibrium temperature rose from 23°C to 33°C over the first 20,000 cycles then remained constant over the whole duration of the test. It was expected that a step reduction in the peak torques during sample cycling of the specimen would occur as crack initiation began, however, no such effect occurred and a gradual reduction in torque was observed. There is a small constant scatter band of + 0.5 Nm in the peak torques. Over the 5.1 million cycles recorded in the test the reduction in peak stress was only 4 Nm in 274 Nm, i.e. less than 1.5%. Some of this reduction is caused by the loss integrity of the rubber interface between the specimen and the grip, and also because of the temperature increase. Although the specimen was closely observed periodically the initial cracking of the specimen was not noticed owing to the difficulty of observing the very fine cracks. However, after 4.5 million cycles the fatigue test was stopped and the specimen very closely examined. Fatigue cracks running from the stationary end of the fatigue machine at two positions predicted by the FE analysis to have the greatest stress concentrations were observed. These extended 135 mm and 76 mm respectively measured from the inner side of the end attachment. The specimen was fatigued further to a total of 5.1 million cycles after which the lengths were 168 mm and 98 mm respectively giving crack growth rates of 54.6 mm/million cycles and 36.7 mm/million cycles for the two cracks. If the assumption is made that the crack growth rate is constant after the initiation of the cracks then initiation would have occurred at the end of the specimen after ~ 1.5 million cycles. However, there is no means of checking this figure since there was no detectable step in the peak torque against number of cycles curve.

Static stiffness measurements, using both the laser optics and the rotation of the torsion head on the cracked fatigue specimen, showed reductions in the torsional rigidity of the specimen of 0.5% to 1%. All of the strain gauges with the exception of gauge 3 had debonded during the fatigue testing. Gauge 3 gave a slope of 13836 Nm/ε equivalent to a reduction in torsional rigidity of 1.5%.

Results for sample 2 (CH2)

Initial torques of + 239 Nm were used in these fatigue tests equivalent to a peak stress of 22.5 MPa and the surface temperature rose from 23°C to 32.5°C over the first 20,000 cycles.

The torques are remarkably constant over the duration of the fatigue test with only a 3.5 Nm difference between the highest and lowest peak torque recorded, and a scatter band of + 0.5 Nm.

In the careful visual examination no cracks were observed at 500 K cycles, whereas at 900 K cycles a 2 mm crack was observed at one end of the specimen growing in from the rubber end fitting. (This is a total crack length of 32 mm if initiated from the end.) At 3.2 million cycles the crack

had grown to 9 mm and by 5 million cycles to 20 mm giving a crack growth rate ~ 7 mm/million cycles. A crack also formed in the other end of the specimen length in the same H channel. Over this fatigue range the peak torques recorded are remarkably stable. The crack growth rates in this sample are a factor of 5 lower than those measured on the first sample stressed at ~ 24 MPa maximum stress. The static stiffness measured after 5 million cycles shows changes in stiffness of only $\pm 0.5\%$.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Static tests on circular section samples of unidirectional glass reinforced epoxide have shown:

- The initial torsional modulus is 4.5 GPa and this falls linearly with increasing torque in the non-linear region.
- The torque twist curve becomes non-linear at stresses ± 23 MPa after which stresses must be calculated using a Nadai correction factor.
- Marked acoustic emission occurs at stresses of ~ 49 MPa and this increases until a longitudinal crack forms along the whole specimen length. Failure occurs at a Nadai corrected torsional stress of 80 MPa.

2. Torsional fatigue tests on circular section samples of unidirectional glass reinforced epoxide have shown:

- The equilibrium surface temperature rises proportionally to the peak fatigue stress amplitude.
- For a given peak stress the equilibrium temperature increases with increasing frequency of test.
- For a given peak stress, lower frequency testing gives higher fatigue lives, as a result of the lower equilibrium temperatures.
- During the fatigue tests at stresses < 30 MPa, the peak torques supported for given angular deflections initially fall until the equilibrium temperature is reached, after which they remain constant until failure occurs.
- At test frequencies of 5 Hz: for fatigue stresses > 30 MPa, the surface temperature does stabilise and failure is by a longitudinal crack forming and running across the whole specimen length.
- At test frequencies of 5 Hz for fatigue stresses > 30 MPa the temperature does not stabilise, and the peak torque decreases with increasing cycles. Thermal runaway at a local spot in the specimen gauge length occurs and a localised radial failure with multiple splitting takes place. As fatigue continues, very high local temperatures of $\sim 170^\circ\text{C}$ can occur.
- There is little scatter in the fatigue results and initial stresses of 22 MPa are predicted to support $\pm 5 \times 10^6$ fatigue

cycles. This stress level is close to the stress at which non-linear effects are first observed in the static torque/strain curves.

3. Tests on the complex H sample have shown:

- The torsional rigidity of this component is $\sim 25.7 \text{ Nm/deg.m}^{-1}$.
- Reasonable agreement to $\pm 8\%$ was obtained between the measured shear strains across the section and those predicted by finite element analysis.
- During fatigue tests at 5.4 Hz a temperature rise of 10°C above ambient was observed at 22-24 MPa peak stress.
- During fatigue, fine cracks were initiated from the ends of the specimen at the radius of the central channel of the complex H. These positions correspond to the positions of the maximum predicted stress.
- The peak torques supported by the section remained remarkably constant over the 5 million fatigue cycles even though fatigue cracking had occurred. It was not possible to measure a 'fatigue failure' by subsequent observation of the peak torques as a function of the number of fatigue cycles during the test.
- Detection of initial cracking was difficult, as the first 30 mm of specimen length at each end of the sample length was held in the grips and was not visible. At 22.5 MPa maximum stress a 2 mm crack was observed at 900 K cycles. The crack subsequently grew at $\sim 7 \text{ mm/million cycles}$. At a peak stress of 24.2 MPa crack growth was $\sim 45 \text{ mm/million cycles}$.
- Static tests on the fatigued complex H specimens indicated changes in stiffness of $\sim 1\%$ compared to the initial tests on the unfatigued samples.
- The torsional static strength of a sample cut from the uncracked section of a fatigued complex H specimen was 1068 Nm equivalent to a predicted maximum shear stress of 82.5 MPa, which is in close agreement with the failure strengths measured on the circular section test pieces.

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FIG. 1. Complex H Section and End Fitting for Torsional Fatigue Testing

FIG. 2. Torque Against Shear Strain for Circular Section Specimen

FIG. 3. Torsional Modulus Against Nadai Corrected Peak Stress

FIG. 4. Torsional Fatigue Measurements at 5Hz, for an Equilibrium Stress of ± 29 MPa

FIG. 5. Torsional Fatigue Measurements at 5Hz, for an Initial Stress of $\pm 50\text{MPa}$

FIG. 6. Nadai Corrected Peak Shear Stress Against Equilibrium Surface Temperature.

FIG. 7. Torsional Fatigue S-N Curve for Unidirectional GRP

Maximum value : 6.339E+05
 Minimum value : 1.218E+04
 Contour levels
 1 : 5.104E+04
 2 : 1.288E+05
 3 : 2.065E+05
 4 : 2.842E+05
 5 : 3.619E+05
 6 : 4.396E+05
 7 : 5.174E+05
 8 : 5.951E+05

FIG. 8. Finite Element Results for Complex H Section